

DIAMAS

Developing Institutional Open Access
Publishing Models to Advance
Scholarly Communication

How to define your Diamond Open Access business case: a six-step guide

Guidance on how to make the case for supporting your Diamond OA publication, project, service or infrastructure

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Whether you are a small OA publisher or a larger service provider aiming to cater to many, this framework can help shape your plans. This resource can also be instrumental in convincing decision-makers to support a new Diamond OA initiative or to significantly upscale or further develop an existing one. While not all the points below may be relevant for smaller requests, addressing all of them becomes increasingly important as the scale of your project grows.

1. The opportunity

Summarise the opportunity that your proposal presents, ideally in one clear sentence, specifying the target audience.

2. The issue

Briefly explain how your proposal addresses a need in the current publishing environment.

3. The objective

Outline your main objective succinctly.

4. The options

Present several courses of action to your decision-maker, including the current situation and up to three alternatives. Briefly explain the pros and cons, costs and timeframes of each choice. Use data if you can to back up your argument.

5. The recommendation

Your proposal should include the following information:

- **Benefits**

List the benefits of your Diamond OA proposal. Think about your decision-maker. What is essential to them?

- **Costs**

Estimate (or assess) the expenses, factoring in both monetary and in-kind resources. What is a realistic timeframe? Describe how you would monitor these elements. Consult with a similar sized/type of journal/publisher/service to help estimate costs if necessary.

- **Assumptions and risks**

List the assumptions (or limitations) behind your Diamond OA publishing proposal. Discuss the risks and explain how you will mitigate these.

- **Key results**

Specify the key result you expect to achieve.

- **Summary of recommendation and benefit**

Summarise the recommendation and highlight its advantages for the intended audience.

6. The summary

Prepare a concise one-page summary of your proposal or business case bringing together the above, and share it with your decision-maker ahead of your meeting.

Be sure to share this with the decision-maker first. You can include steps 1-5 afterwards as background in an Annex, or not at all.

The summary should include:

- The one-sentence opportunity
- The alternatives, including pros and cons
- The recommendation

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